

A BRIEF STUDY OF CONSUMER'S PERSEPECTIVE TOWARDS E-CORNERS OF STATE BANK OF INDIA IN CHANDIGARH

Pooja Bhanot, Assistant Professor

University School of Business, Chandigarh University

Punjab, India

poojabhanot.usb@cumail.in

Abstract

Objective: This paper discusses the the various alternative channels of banking, provided by the banks in order to increase thier customers' satisfaction, reduce costs, and improve the working of banks

Method and statistical analysis: The primary data has been collected from the customers through questionnaires. Random sampling technique was used. The sample size of customer respondents is 50, who are using e-corner at university campus.

The questionnaire for the customers was based on five variables: usage, technical, ambience, comparison and overall satisfaction. The information collected by the questionnaire was entered in IBM SPSS Statistics version 16.0. Data analysis was done by applying various statistical tests like chi square and factor analysis.

Findings: it was observed that there are customers who come to banks only to avail basic srrervices, which can also be availed from e-Corners. But customers do not use these channels as they still prefer to go the brick and mortar branch.

Application/Improvements: In order to increase the usage of these e-Corners, several initiatives are taken up by the **banks**. It also found that e-Corners are capabke of

reducing additional costs of the banks, thus they are cost effective solutions.

Keywords: alternate banking channels, financial inclusion, e-lobby, e-corner

I. INTRODUCTION

Competition and computerization have changed the Indian banking scenario. Manual ledgers are replaced by desk top computing and electronic statements of accounts are replacing saving bank passbooks. Plastic cards have made the wallet thinner. Initially bank branches were computerized on standalone basis. The ATMS were also standalone ATMs. When banks adopted core banking systems, it resulted in networking of branches as well as the ATMs across the country. With the help of technology, the banking industry can develop or expand into new channels to survive in the current competitive environment. Any new channel involves cost and in alternate channels, technology plays a vital role in terms of providing a near to branch experience to the well-informed wealth management customer. With the help of information technology and communication technology, banks in India have introduced many new products and services using modern delivery channels

such as ATM, interne, mobile telephones and e-corners. This study focuses on the concept of e-Corner as an alternative channel of banking.

II. Research methodology

This study is based on the onsite e-Corner of Panjab University branch of State bank of India, Chandigarh. The primary data has been collected from the customers through questionnaires. Random sampling technique was used. The sample size of customer respondents is 50, who are using e-corner at university campus.

A self administered structured questionnaire based on 5 point likert scale was used to record the responses of customers of the selected bank branch. The questionnaire for the customers was based on five variables: usage, technical, ambience, comparison and overall satisfaction.

The information collected by the questionnaire was entered in IBM SPSS Statistics version 16.0. Data analysis was done by applying various statistical tests like chi square and factor analysis.

The results of the study shows that ambience of the e-Corner have significant positive association with the age (Likelihood ratio 45.134, $df=20$, $p=.001$), and gender of

III. Descriptive Statistics

In the survey the study of respondents' demographic data was vital, because these data could further help to understand and study the perceptions of respondents towards the e-Corner.

- Mean of age of the respondents is 1.52, which means that most of the respondents belong to age group 18-30 years.
- Mean of education level of the of the customer respondents is 2.34
- Mean of occupation of the customer respondents is 2.40
- Mean of monthly income of the customer respondents is 1.56
- On an average, respondents have given negative responses towards the usage as they don't use e-corners frequently and for all basic services.
- On an average, respondents have given neutral responses regarding technical, ambience, overall satisfaction and comparison, as the mean value is slightly more than 3.

IV. Results

therespondents (Likelihood ratio 23.008, $df=10$, $p=.011$). However the relationship is redundant, in case of ambience and age, and quite weak in case of gender and ambience.

Ambience*Age

So in nutshell, we can say that customers are using e-Corners primarily for cash withdrawal service, and not for the other basic services.

V. Conclusion and suggestions

In this study, an attempt was made to understand the various alternative channels of banking, provided by the banks in order to increase their customers' satisfaction, reduce costs, and improve the working of banks. During the study, it was observed that there are customers who come to banks only to avail basic services, which can also be availed from e-Corners. But customers do not use these channels as they still prefer to go the brick and mortar branch. In order to increase the usage of these e-Corners, several initiatives are taken up by the banks. It also found that e-Corners are capable of reducing additional costs of the banks, thus they are cost effective solutions. Apart from this a survey was also conducted to know the customers perception about e-Corner at Panjab University branch of State bank of India. Since the data was categorical, chi-square test was used to find out the relationship between various demographic factors and other variables. Reduntant and weak association was found between age and ambience and gender and ambience respectively. So we can conclude in the end that these e-Corners are less expensive than new brick and mortar bank branches and offer the basic services and will play an important role in increasing the financial inclusion. It is a gift of modern technology which is a boon to the banks. However, initiatives from the banks sides are required to be taken in order to create awareness among customers so that they can use e-Corners without any hitch.

VI. Limitations of the study

The study is based on data available in Panjab University branch of state bank of India only. Its applicability to the other parts of the country may not be assured. The sample size, which is 50, is quite small. Therefore, the output will represent more or less a true picture of the customers as a whole.

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